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The Book of Ruth on Widow's Challenges, and Pastoral Counselling for Effective Widow Empowerment among Nigerian Christians

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Abstract

Pastoral counseling as a practice of ministry and discipline, serves as a theological bridge discipline connecting ministry, marriage and family therapy. Among the points in Theo-psychology of Pastoral Counseling is the fact that the Bible presents God's recipe for wholesome living. Many tragic and traumatising circumstances in life befall people and Christians are not exempted. Widowhood is one of such traumas. Widowhood is an inevitable tragic human phenomenon which nearly every married person experiences. While the degree of pain varies according to age and other socio-economic factors, the gravity of its trauma is evident in the usual immediate sympathetic response to widows or widowers. Scholarly engagements of the book of Ruth have focused on many areas such as Davidic ancestry, levirate, land redemption, hesed-kindness, polemics, widowhood and others. While scholarly works abound on widowhood, not much has been done in relating widow empowerment schema of the book of Ruth to pastoral counseling. Using descriptive method and narrative criticism, this article analyses the text of Ruth to expound different modes of widow empowerment as tool for effective pastoral care and counseling on widowhood. It does so based on findings which reveal that widow challenges vary from different cultures and social settings but the book of Ruth provides a veritable and inclusive empowerment pattern.

Keywords: Widow's empowerment, Pastoral care/counseling, Book of Ruth, Widowhood in Christendom

Introduction

Widowhood, a phenomenon where a married person loses the spouse, is something that transcends culture, ethnicity, religion, educational background and socio-economic state, thus, it is a global phenomenon. It is an ageless and almost unavoidable reality for a married person that usually comes with its attendant challenges of agony and pains. It is a phenomenon that can happen at any stage in the life of a married person. But due to culture and traditions in some places (especially in Africa and Asia), the agony of widowhood is abysmally enormous especially for a widow. A widow is described as a silent victim in terms of socio-economic, psychological and human right violation in many African countries. They face economic hardship and emotional imbalances coupled with social victimisations of all sort (Oluwatunbi, 2009,149). Widowhood can result due to many causes such as poverty, sickness, road traffic accident and violence. As a nation, Nigeria has witnessed so many security issues in recent years the result of which has also increased the cases of widowhood.

While widowhood readily attracts sympathy, some of their peculiar needs such as psycho-emotional needs, sexual needs, security needs and others are not met by the various humanitarian gestures from the society. Brian Croft and Austin Walker reinforce this, when they state that few circumstances in life can be as devastating as the loss of a husband. They further aver that though a husband also goes through grief and intensely feels the sense of desolation arising from the demise of a wife; the Bible has comparatively little to say about living as a widower, while it has so much to say about being a widow. One inferable reason for this distinction, perhaps, is the fact that a widower is not in the same vulnerable and precarious position as a widow (Croft, & Walker, 2015, 15).

Further to this, many widows are exposed to degrading experiences such as sexual harassment, food and financial insecurity, accusations or maltreatment from the late husband's family, sexual immorality and so on. Ordinarily, the situation of a widow elicits sympathy even if the said widow is financially stable. Beatrice Schwartz, A widowed healthcare professional, asserts that no one can prepare a widow for what she faces. Unfortunately, still, her agony seems not to be felt by the world around her (Stockton, 2015).

The book of Ruth is a short Biblical narrative. Though small in volume, the book addresses critical social and economic issues. In the pages of this unique text are issues such as migration, inter-communal relationship, famine, harvest, widows' welfare as well as divine providence. Ruth reveals that even in situations of spiritual apostasy and gross moral decadence, God looks for devout individuals upon whom He can bestow His blessing. The book projects the sovereign acts of God in the lives of self-effacing and unassuming individuals at the time of the Judges, the charismatic leaders of pre-monarchical Israel. The amazing story narrates how a family from Bethlehem, in the horrible days of judges receives God's blessing in an unexpected way when gross moral disorder and spiritual decline held sway.

While scholars have ascribed different themes to the book, Ruth narrative implicitly discusses widows' challenges and provides helpful tips that offer framework for widow counseling and empowerment. Since Pastoral Counseling is a kind relationship or activity in which a pastor or minister assists individuals, couples and families resolve their emotional, relational and psychosocial issues with the use of the Bible as primary manual (Odeleye, 2017), application of the book of Ruth, especially its widow empowerment scheme, is therefore appropriate in pastoral counseling and widowhood. Thus, this article explores widow empowerment in the book of Ruth as pastoral counseling tool.

Pastoral Theology and Counseling

It is said that pastoral theology is difficult to define with precision owing to the ambiguity of its boundaries with related disciplines such as practical theology and applied theology (Tidball, 1998, 493). But it concerns the theory and the practice of Christian ministry as right practice proceeds from right belief. Pastoral theology has to do with the relationship between theology and pastoral task; providing theological foundation for pastoral ministry and stimulating reflections on pastoral experience, and at the same time, reflecting on theology from a pastoral perspective (Tidball, 1998). Primarily, Pastoral Theology is concerned with three major areas of

local church ministry which are: leadership, pastoral care, and public ministry (Hill, n.d). Thus pastoral counselling fittingly subsumes under pastoral care which is an arm of pastoral theology. Pastoral counselling is about care for the total man- body, soul/spirit. "Pastor" is a Latin word for 'shepherd' (Hill, n.d) and it literally means nurturer, watchman or care giver (Odeleye, 2022). The role of a pastor as primarily parental is better indicated in Roman Catholic tradition by the priestly title 'Father'. While biblical warrant for such a parental emphasis exists, the Protestant preference is that of regarding the pastor as an under-shepherd of Jesus Christ. Thus, N. Pam's description of Pastoral Counselling as a type of counselling or psychotherapy in which knowledge and standards from theology and behavioural sciences are employed in working with people... and cultural systems to attain healing and development; and Odeleye's submission that, it is a helping relationship wherein a pastor assists individuals, couples and families to resolve their emotional, relational and psychosocial issues, using the Bible as fundamental manual, are apt about care giving (Pam, 2013; Odeleye, 2022). Widows, undoubtedly, are a group needing pastoral counseling.

The Book of Ruth

The book of Ruth is a narrative of how a family from Bethlehem migrates from Bethlehem to Moab during the anarchistic period of the Judges. The story is built around three main characters: Naomi, Ruth and Boaz. Elimelech, his wife Naomi and two sons: Mahlon and Chilion leave their homeland to seek food security and succor in Moab. The migration is as a result of famine. The irony of the matter, however, is that they migrate from Bethlehem- *house of food* on account of famine to settle in the land of Moab. Mahlon and Chilion marry Moabite women: Ruth and Orpah. But soon afterwards, the man Elimelech dies, leaving his wife, Naomi, widowed. Naomi loses not only her husband but also her two sons who die leaving her and two widowed daughters-in-law. Three widows are left in the family. In fact, Naomi, the wife of the Elimelech cries that she has become empty (1:21). Following the tragedy, Naomi decides to return back to Bethlehem her homeland. Ruth, one of her widowed daughters-in-law, returns with her to Bethlehem to begin a new life.

However, unless an intervention comes from someone to support these distressed women, their only expectation is a life of destitution and solitude. God actually intervenes through the agency of empowerment. Although the book is placed in the historical period of the judges- a time characterised by apostasies, irresponsibility, cruelty and anarchy, Reed finds that the place of God is very prominent in the book. According to him, different names of God are used profusely in the book and on two occasions, the author speaks of God's sovereign, superintending grace on behalf of the main characters: Naomi, Ruth and Boaz (2000, 415-429). Mathew Micahel also substantiates this when he states that one of three theologies that can be highlighted from Ruth is that of divine providence. According to him, the book emphasises the act of providence in Naomi and Ruth's return to Bethlehem and ultimately in the meeting of Ruth and Boaz (2015, 170). As such, by divine providence and twist of events the desolate widows receive God's blessing in an unexpected way in the age of gross moral disorder and spiritual decline. The wealthy man, Boaz, recognises Ruth's dedication, genuine love and commitment. He shows her

compassion and in the course of time, marries her. The union produces the grandparents of the great king David.

The book of Ruth is a simple story. In it are no battles or military conquests. There is just a poignant, powerful story about a pair of widowed women struggling to survive during a difficult time. From the story emerges the fact that God is at work and He quietly directs things behind the scene to bring about deliverance to clean the mess created in the book of Judges; and prefiguring David as man for the job (Hayes, & Duvall, 2011, 157-158).

While in the Jewish Bible-*Tanakh*, Ruth is after Proverbs (at the head of a sub-group of books called *Megillot* or 'scrolls') and before Song of Songs, it is placed in between Judges and 1 Samuel in the Christian cannon. Insertion of the story of Ruth between the books of Judges and Samuel in the Christian scripture derives from the Septuagint and Vulgate, which is more or less a chronological order. This location somewhat connects Ruth with the poem of the virtuous woman in proverb 31 and the Song of Songs wherein the woman takes leading role in the relationship (Longman III, & Dillard, 2013, 144). This probably gives hint about the role of woman in the book. As regards its literature, the book is a literary masterpiece arranged into four chapters carved almost like a four-act drama. It has a clear opening and a concluding paragraph in each chapter (or scene), and each one centres on important discourse (Arnold & Beyer, 2015, 162). Unlike Characters in other historical books, the book of Ruth is not about great political or religious figures like kings, judges, prophets or priests. Naomi's husband, Elimelech, and his family, are average Israelites negotiating their way through the day-to-day affairs of life (Arnold & Beyer, 2015). Ruth describes simple and rustic life. While it has moral teachings about God, it apparently teaches about women's resilience especially when they work in harmony. Though it is a book in patriarchal epoch, it describes womenfolk as taking advantage of patriarchal structures in pursuit of survival (Phiri, 2006, 319). Not only this, it as well pictures how women, particularly widows can be empowered, and how the empowered women can transform their social outlook.

Different purposes have been associated with the book. Matthew Michael notes as follows: Some have seen the purpose of the book to be romance or propaganda aimed at justifying marriage to gentile women. In this wise, the book is believed by those sharing this view to be a polemic against the pious Ezra's reformation which objects to marriage of Israelite men to foreign women (Ezra 9). Evangelical Christians, on the other hand, understand the book to be dealing with divine providence in the inclusion of gentiles in the family line of David and ultimately, Christ. In this connect, the book of Ruth serves as prototype of the inclusion of the gentile world in the divine plan of human salvation which is expounded in the New Testament (2015). Others also note that the book is written to stir faith in the hearts of the returning exile; while some others hold the opinion that the book is a *midrash* on a Bethlehem fertility cult myth. Still further, reversal of fortune (emptiness-fullness), demonstration of levirate, *hesed*-kindness and *go'el*-redemption are various purposes advanced for the book. However, Olawale Peter (2021) argues that widow empowerment is a dominant motif in the book. His widow empowerment scheme in the text provides counselling tool that can be engaged in pastoral counselling.

Widowhood and Widow Challenges

Usually, widows are socially excluded category in many societies. Narayan affirms that data suggest that in many cultures across the globe and among the poor, to become a widow is tantamount to “social death.” This is so as widows are seen as omen of death and misfortune, and they are considered a burden, as useless, and as easy prey. She further affirms that combination of social prejudices, traditions, and lack of accountability on the part of state institutions demonstrates why widows face great risk of social exclusion and poverty (1999, 205). Mary Nwogu comments further that for a woman who loses her husband, there abound experiences of serious agony and sadness which get further complicated by both secluded and communal mistreatment she faces. Widows are abused physically, economically, sexually and psychologically (2015). This makes pastoral counseling based on integrated or holistic widow empowerment to be of urgent and immense imperativeness to address different spheres of widows’ lives.

Problems Associated with Widowhood

The trauma that comes on women when she gets news of her husband’s demise is just the beginning of many challenges to come. Blessed A. Enekeme says when a woman cries profusely on hearing of the husband’s death, she does that not only for the death, but also for fear of the type of trauma she is soon to face from the society, especially from her in-laws (2015, 2). Thus, shock, fears, stigmatization, depression, aloofness, poor health, difficulty in finance are some of the immediate and remote effects of widowhood. Some of these are further itemized and briefly discussed.

Poverty

Poverty goes beyond finance only. For a normal person, well-being or good life is multidimensional and has both material and psychological dimensions. Well-being involves peaceful mind, good health, sense of belonging in a community, safety, freedom to choose and act, reliable and steady source of income as well as food. As Deepa Narayan puts it; being poor involves painful and humiliating stigma and this perpetually leads to segregation (1999, 199). It predisposes the poor to insolence, disgrace, and callous treatment by both individual and communal agents within the society from whom they seek help. Many widows in traditional societies have this to. They have next- to-no rights of inheritance in their father’s holdings, and in instances where they can inherit, it is not on an equal basis with male siblings. Since there are no inheritance rights for the widows, they normally depend mostly on the charity of their husband’s families who are mostly hostile. “Property-grabbing” and “chasing off” are things that widows usually experience. The combination of illiteracy and absence of training in any trade further worsen situation and further aggravate the poverty level of widows in many climes. Therefore, widowhood reduces a widow to a beggarly status especially where the husband is the sole breadwinner.

Difficulty in Remarriage

Another serious and yet often overlooked problem of the widows is remarriage. On many occasions, a widower is left with other wives (in the event of a polygamy), or may remarry. The situation is not the same for widows. In the event of a polygyny, they are left in competition with co-wives for property. Also in a monogamous marriage, most widows find it difficult to remarry due to certain constraints of male-dominated society. Whereas a widower is usually encouraged to remarry as soon as possible, widows in many societies are ostracized for attempting the same. Sometimes also, widowers may find a willing marital partner but if she has children, difficulty ensues because the man may not want added financial and social burden of providing for the new wife and her Children.

Health Effects

Ill health is not far from a place where poverty abound. Due to shock, inadequate diet, poor housing, impediment to decent health care, susceptibility to attack and dehumanizing widowhood rites experienced by many widows, they become victims of serious health issues such as chronic depression and infections. Also in some places, compelling the widows into sexual acts with nominated personages in the bid to expel malevolent spirits and cutting her hair with unsterile object predispose them to sexually transmitted infections and other scary diseases like HIV/AIDS. Unfortunately, when such happens, the widow is said to be getting consequences of some secret sin, when in actual fact, she is just a victim of circumstance. Akinbi (2015) also notes that many of them are diagnosed more with hypertension in consequence of burdens they bear unassisted.

Psychological Effect

One other unpleasant consequence of widowhood is emotional derangement and psychological instability that many widows experience and which predispose them to shock, momentary or long-lasting memory loss (amnesia). This happens as Gbile Akanni appropriately remarks that "because of certain societal customs and beliefs that are contrary to the welfare of widows, they are often looked down upon, shamefully-treated and denied their rights" (2001, 20). Many widows lose sense of worth and see themselves as inferior. Apart from this, loneliness and fears are other psychological problems a widow encounters. When the husband dies, a woman misses many things like companionship, responsibility of the children's welfare, consultation on crucial matters and decision making. Thus, some develop Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) and some consider option of suicidal attempt. Summing it up, Okorafor Nkemdilim posits that the greatest problem of all that a widow goes through is emotional (2011). A widow also says unless one has another widow to talk to, there is no one out there who really understands a widow's crippling feeling...There is no one to express feelings to either good or bad (Stockton, 2015).

Social Disconnection

Married women are respected and held in esteem in the society. But once a woman loses her husband, she becomes a sexualised being. Writing about a socialite woman who woke from sleep

and found her husband next to her dead, Stockton says she remarks that she is now a citizen and member of WOW (World of Widows) (2015). This typifies the first feeling of many widows. A widow becomes single woman again and experiences life like single ladies (never married) do. She may not be able to freely talk with a man again so that she is not perceived to be luring and seducing him. Inadvertently, her interactions are truncated in the society because she is being watched by everyone around. Other social challenges include discrimination, ostracism, oppression, dissociation from social groups and restriction from speaking publicly.

Impact on children

Many widows face double trauma-personal trauma and that of the children especially if they are young. The responsibility of assisting them cope with current situation both physically and psychologically rests on her. In this case, she needs to assist them handle the emotional hurt, pains of separation and get the grip of the reality at hand. She will also need to answer tough questions even though some of those questions might be questions she herself is asking and getting no answers to. Aside this, withdrawal from school is the problems widows face with children. In most cases girl children are usually affected first as they are required to care for other siblings while their mother engages in menial jobs or begs for money. Such girls who are denied education are in all likelihood going to become child-brides and child-mothers, a situation that readily predisposes them to reproductive health challenges and limits their opportunities for economic independence. Lack of fatherly contribution to child rising and discipline may also result in some children becoming juvenile delinquent.

Apart from poverty, all the aforementioned challenges can confront a widow regardless of her socio-economic status. Across many cultural and political settings, 'voicelessness' and powerlessness are some shared elements underlining widows' marginalisation. As such, every widow in every society needs counseling, especially pastoral counseling. But as proposed in this article, using the widow empowerment scheme expounded from the book of Ruth is a handy tool in pastoral counseling and widow Challenges.

Widow Empowerment in the Book of Ruth

The book of Ruth has attracted attention as a result of which different themes have been associated with it. But certain things make it clear that the book is about widows and how they are empowered to live a meaningful and productive life. For instance, two among the three main character of the narrative are widows (Naomi and Ruth). Secondly, four of all six women mentioned by name in the book are widows. Finally, the book focuses on how destitute and hapless widows' situations changed for better through the agency of the third main character-Boaz thus, ultimately showing that the book is about widow empowerment.

When empowerment is mentioned, especially widow empowerment, the first thing that comes to the mind of many is giving of financial aid. But quite frankly, empowerment is about the factor of motivation which is constantly needed in order to help stimulate a course of action in an attempt to change and make a perpetual condition better for the purpose of achieving the desired objectives (Aluko, 2007). Empowerment gives people room not only to define themselves but also

to create their own personalities and be the product of a deliberate plan which may be externally initiated by agents of empowerment or lobbied by people who are disempowered (Hamelink, 1994). The book of Ruth demonstrates different modes or forms of widow empowerment as examined below.

Self-empowerment

Ruth 1:6 *Then she arose with her daughters-in-law, in order to return from the field of Moab: because she heard in the field of Moab that the LORD had visited his people in giving them food.*

Ruth 2:7 *She said, 'Please let me glean and gather among the sheaves behind the harvesters.' She went into the field and has worked steadily from morning till now, except for a short rest in the shelter."*

Self-empowerment begins from self-discovery. Scally and Hopson describe self-empowerment as situation whereby someone progressively assumes better responsibility over his or her life generally (1981, 57). This has to do with understanding one's present condition: limitation and challenges, then possible options or way out. It concerns knowing one's ability and opportunity, and then the propensity to spur the ability in pursuit of the opportunity.

Widows usually feel down cast with labile emotion as a result of shock, loneliness, fears, other factors. Some recede to seclusion, aloofness and despair. Ruth 1:6 reports that Naomi rises to return to Bethlehem after she hears that Yahweh has sent help to His people. Earlier, Naomi has lost everyone except her daughters-in-law she intends to send them away too. Thus, as a stranger in Moab, she is completely vulnerable and as an old widow, she is destitute. But on hearing the news of God's provision in Bethlehem, and being aware of legal provision of support system for the widows in Israel.

Elimelch leaves his homeland בֵּית לֶחֶם *Bethlehem* (house of bread) to go to שְׂדֵי מוֹאָב (field or open country) of Moab (1:1). While a house provides protection and warmth, *hd,f' an open field* exposes one to danger and predation. But Naomi,

כִּי שָׁמְעָה בְּשַׂדֵּי מוֹאָב כִּי־פָקַד יְהוָה אֶת־עַמּוֹ לַחֵת לָהֶם לֶחֶם:

because she heard ...that the LORD had visited His people in giving them food, rises (קום) to return to her once forsaken homeland where she has a redeemable family property. This shows Naomi as not giving-in to despair. She innovatively thinks of a way out. Whatever help she later gets is because she first of all empowers herself by choosing life rather than death, hope rather than despair and relief (in Bethlehem) rather than suffering (in Moab). The same is true of Ruth, another self-empowered widow in the book.

Ruth decides to return with Naomi against all persuasion to do otherwise. Providentially, their return happens to be during barley harvest. Ruth wastes no time waiting for some manna to fall from heaven. She swings into action of self-support. The verbs לָקַט *glean* is used in the book of Ruth more than any other book (cf 2:2, 3, 7,6 15, 17, 23). In each case gleaning is associated with

either Ruth or Naomi or both of them. She goes to the field which would later better their fortune. It is unlikely that Boaz would come looking for Ruth if she does not take the initial step of doing something to help her situation. This is what self-empowerment entails. The tenor of the book of Ruth clearly reveals that Naomi's decision to return to Bethlehem and Ruth's decision to go with her and her subsequent decision to glean from farms determines the narrative trajectory of the book. Their decisions are self-motivated and this becomes their sources of livelihood and future joy. This, in this writer's view, indicates self-empowerment

In pastoral counseling, widows should be brought to the awareness of the fact of self-empowerment. Each widow should know her major problem or biggest challenge. Her attempt to address this may beckon on others for help. Therefore, counselor should help every widow to look inward to see what she is capable of; and outward to see what is available in order to effect a positive change in her situation. Aloofness and self-pity will do no good and will only make the widow suffer to no end while she lives.

Economic empowerment

In patriarchal society, the husband is usually the breadwinner of the family. Provision of basic needs and financing the home all rest squarely on him. So, his demise spells doom on the family economy. This is very true of many African families even up till now. Many lose not only the source of finance but also the family properties to unkind in-laws. This explains why financial support is the first thing that comes to the mind of many people when widow's care is mentioned. Ruth by providence comes to a wealthy man's farm. The man, Boaz, speaks kindly to Ruth, gives her lot of grain (for her and Naomi) and makes provision for her protection. But whatever the quantity of gift, it would only for a while. The two widows will soon go back to penury. From their conversation and from his observation, Boaz recognizes ability to work. Knowing this, he instituted a lasting means of livelihood for the two widows by letting Ruth glean continually in his field till the end of harvest. This is a gainful employment rather than momentary gift of money. By that offer, Ruth's chance of great return is high. First the problem of moving from one field to another and the problem of competition with other gleaners are removed. Secondly, great return is guaranteed since Boaz expressly tells his worker to deliberately leave grains for her; and thirdly she has good working environment with accommodating 'co-workers'

This is clear depiction of economic empowerment for young and agile person, where they are not just given some money or materials that would be exhausted within a short period of time. Bearing in mind that the qualification for certain opportunities in the ancient times was usually a matter of status: whether one is male or female, slave or free person, indigene or stranger and son. So as a widow, Ruth is mainly qualified for gleaning and Boaz makes that easy.

While concerned individuals, group or religious bodies may offer financial or materials gifts to widows, the pastor or counsellor should adequately prepare the mind of the widows to take charge of herself and expand her financial capability rather than living on people's charity. What we see is not just giving of material gifts to the widows, but giving of opportunity for the widows to explore and expend ability. The pastor can enhance this not only through counselling but also

by facilitating her connection to job opportunities as some widows possess skills, ability or certificate which can afford them decent jobs and earn them a living.

Social empowerment

Emerging from the text of Ruth is another empowerment framework known as social empowerment. It is very possible for a person to be empowered or 'disempowered from social factors such as culture, religion, law, custom/practices, social roles, social stratification and interpersonal relationship. When people are culturally or religiously considered as a social misfit, their social status naturally depreciates and this will affect their interpersonal relationship with other members of the society and ultimately their productivity.

In many African cultural settings, widows do not enjoy equal status as other women in the society. They usually get treated either with pity or disdain. Sometimes, they are even considered as evil omen and bad company. So, many widows internalize this stereotypic view of their person, take it as norm, and suppress their feeling, ambitions and interest. Therefore, any action or an attempt to correct social phenomena that prevent widows from maximally enjoying their potential and their good wishes is social empowerment.

In Ruth (1:8-9), Naomi gives her daughters-in-law the chance to go and remarry. Culturally, Ruth and Orpah could not have remarried as they remain members of Elimelech's family. As the only consenting family member available, Naomi reserves the right to allow or prevent their remarriage, but she chooses instead, to free them and grant them the choice of choosing their marriage partners. While Ruth, out of uncommon loyalty, commitment and perhaps sympathy does not take this offer, Orpah does. This contrasts negatively with the practices in many societies where the woman would be held 'hostage' by the late husband's family simply because she refuses to marry within the family. One interesting thing about Ruth narrative here is that it shows that in widowhood, there are choices. Both Ruth and Orpah make different choices.

Levirate, and the legal framework providing support and security for the poor and destitute, are other notable social institutions in Israel that feature to empower widows in the book of Ruth. The law of Redemption is one of the institutions in the book of Ruth and does not have much to do with widowhood. But in the narrative of Ruth, redemption is closely tied to widows' welfare. The legal provision about land redemption is contained in (Lev. 25:23-24) and that of levirate in (Deut. 25:5-10).

These laws basically function to preserve the name and guard the properties of family in Israel. Due to insolvency, Naomi wants to trade a portion of land belonging to her late husband. It seems that at the death of Elimelech, the property passed to Mahlon so, his widow Ruth is included in the redemption responsibility (Reed, 2000, 415-429). Boaz buys the land and takes Ruth as his wife. These social institutions of redemption and levirate marriage are graphically demonstrated in Ruth, restoring the lost hope of remarriage to Ruth and hope of economic sustenance to Naomi. The legal framework providing support for the widows and other poor members of Israelite society is noteworthy too. It is legal because the instruction is contained in the legal document of Leviticus and Deuteronomy (Lev. 29: Deut. 25:5-10). Israelites were not to harvest to the edge of the field. This is seen in practical term in the book of Ruth with the farm owner going beyond the

stipulation of law. It is no coincidence that three important social institutions are brought to bear in a single narrative and all directly effecting the welfare of widows. This lays bare the widow empowerment motif of the book of Ruth.

Another evidence of social widow empowerment motif in Ruth is in “care for the elderly” parents. Naomi loses her two sons who should have provided succour for her in old age. But one of the two daughters-in-law takes up the care of Naomi at old age. This, no doubt, is great refreshment as the grand children who should have been her crown at old age are presently lacking (Pro 17:6). As an elderly widow, the support of the children and the pleasure of having grand children around strengthen and help remove boredom. Ruth adequately fills this vacuum in Naomi’s life. Not only is Ruth present with Naomi, she also gives her a son who become a hope of sustenance in old age. The words of the women of Bethlehem perfectly elucidate this fact:

The women said to Naomi: "Praise be to the LORD, who this day has not left you without a kinsman-redeemer. May he become famous throughout Israel! He will renew your life and sustain you in your old age. For your daughter-in-law, who loves you and who is better to you than seven sons, has given him birth." (Ruth 4:14-15)

Psycho-emotional empowerment

Arguably, Psycho-emotional challenge is the most disturbing difficulty that widows face. Financial and social support issues are no problem for some widows based on their race, level of education, type of job, the society they live in; or their social class. However, emotional problem is almost universally shared by all widows regardless of class or financial status. Especially in places like Nigeria where many become widow before the age of fifty, the shock, loneliness and fears of all sort result in serious emotional breakdown. This is further compounded by obnoxious and dehumanizing widowhood rites that emotionally paralyse some widows irrevocably. In addition, some widows become objects of sexual harassment. In their vulnerability, they give in to ‘cheap’ sex which leaves them feeling used up and further dejected. In frustration, some lose sense of dignity. Thus, the psycho-emotional challenges that widows go through is hard to fathom, and this makes psycho-emotional empowerment one of the most important forms of widow empowerment.

Two passages prominently elucidate Psycho-emotional empowerment in Ruth. The first is Ruth’s

classical statement in (Ruth1:16-17) where Ruth cleaves ^(רָבַדְתִּי) in 1:14 to her elderly mother-in-

law with a solemn oath of loyalty and allegiance. Quite frequently in the Old Testament, ^{רָבַדְתִּי} is used in relation to physical objects getting stuck to each other, or affectionate and loyal clinging to somebody. It is expected that Man cleaves to his wife (Gen 2:24). This action which verse 14 demonstrates later gets expression in 16-17. Naomi who earlier blames her woes on God (1:13, 20-21), later has her fortune changed for better because of Ruth presence (4:15b). She sees no hope of remarriage for her young widowed daughters-in-law in Israel (1:11-13), but when psychologically empowered, she becomes aware of the possibility of Boaz marrying Ruth (3:1). Ruth’s decision to follow Naomi back to Bethlehem was not basically to provide economic support but emotional one by her presence. The book shows that life becomes worth living and

future worth facing for Naomi because Ruth is there. Here we see Ruth empowering Naomi psycho-emotionally. Some widows really do not have financial difficulty nor do they suffer cultural dehumanisation. They simply need someone to share their feelings with, someone to talk to, or just companions in the time when their emotions run high.

Another notable psycho-emotional empowering phenomenon in Ruth is in Boaz and Ruth's meeting. Ruth is not only a young widow but also a foreigner in Israel thus, she is of lower status than that of hired servants of Boaz (2:13). But when Boaz comes to the farm, noticing Ruth, he

speaks kindly to her calling her בְּתוּרַי "my daughter" (2:8). This appellation means so much to Ruth. This is the first and only place (apart from figurative expressions) in Hebrew Bible where this appellation is used for someone without biological relationship. More than any other person in the Hebrew Bible, she is called by that phrase (1:11-13; 2:2, 8, 22; 3:1, 10-11, 16, 18). More so, the

person addressing Ruth is אִישׁ גְּבוּר חָיִל a man of wealth and influence (2:1). Meanwhile Ruth

calls herself שִׁפְחָה *maidservant* (2:13), a more menial term than אָמָה another Hebrew word for *maidservant*. Thus, when Boaz calls her that, it feels elating and affectionate. Naturally, widows need psycho-emotional empowerment from people around them like family members, co-workers, church members, employers and so on. Some just want reassurance of the dignity of their personhood. A pastoral counselor is adequately equipped to do this

Sexual Empowerment

One area usually overlooked in widowhood phenomenon is that of their sexual need. Rebecca Chalker laments that despite groundbreaking research revealing that orgasm in both sexes is triggered by the same mechanism, many people almost universally, still perceive sexuality of women not as powerful, not as fascinating, not as profound as that of men. She notes that from the ancient times, the sexual organs together with sexual response of men have been idealised, while the women's own have been regarded as the less-perfect equivalents. Consequently today, we are in the age where sexual relationships are under what is basically a male model of human sexuality (Chalker, 1994). Many judge a widow's need of remarriage on the basis of whether she has child(ren) or not. But the book of Ruth

The narrative evokes some sexual nuances. For example, the clause וַתִּגְלֹחַ ; פְּרָגְלָתָיו and uncover *his feet* in 3:7, describes where Ruth uncovers and sleeps. The term "feet" is sometimes employed as euphemism to denote sexual organs. Edward Campbell (1975, 121) explains that this noun relates to the common noun *regel* "foot" in etymology, and it can serve euphemistically to designate the penis or the vulva, either as the urinary opening or as sexual organs (Judg 3:24; I Sam 24:3; II Kings 18:27; Isa 36: 12; Isa 7:20; Ezek 16:25). Thus, the provocative sexual overtures, and later marriage that ensued (3:1-18) justifies a widow's need of sexual relationship which should not be denied or suppressed. The text however, demonstrates that sexual activities should be properly situated in the context of marriage only. A widow is not to be sexually empowered in the sense of satisfying her sexual need outside marriage but should be encouraged to remarry if young enough to marry.

As a spiritual therapist, a pastor counselor has the mandate of helping people through and out of their trauma. Widowhood is a traumatic experience and as such, widows need pastoral counseling. However, a counselor must understand that all widows should not be treated homogeneously. By this, it means that the need of different categories of widow varies. These variations depend on the age, cultural settings, financial and social status of the widows. Therefore, engaging widow pastoral counseling using the widow empowerment framework expounded from the book of Ruth will help counselor to individualise widows in counseling and help to provide focused and effective therapy.

Further, the book of Ruth which has not been much read into widow support system can now be actively engaged in counseling widows. The narrative is clear and evidence based. Apart from assurances and promises from other passages of the Holy Bible, counselor can focus the attention of widows on the graphical fact of God's help for widows (both young and hold) in the book of Ruth.

Conclusion

This article examines the book of Ruth. It observes that though different themes such as levirate, Davidic lineage history, polemic against prohibition of foreign marriage, and so on have been associated with the book; a major and dominant motif of the book is widow empowerment. Different factors affect the experiences of some widows. One of such is culture. In some cultures, widows face harsh and dehumanising treatments, victimisation and even accusation as one responsible for husband's death. Furthermore, among cultures where harsh treatments are meted out to widows, the degree of harshness varies. Apart from culture, social status such as level of education, type of job, level of finance etc. also affect widows.

About five empowerment frameworks emerge from the book of Ruth which are: economic, social, psycho-emotional, sexual and self-empowerments. Since Christians are from different race, cultures and social backgrounds, one or more of these widow empowerment frameworks will apply to an individual widow in any culture or social setting. The paper argues therefore, that knowledge of these widow empowerment schemes provides a veritable tool for pastoral counseling in providing spiritual therapy and succour to Christian (and possibly non-Christian) widows of all categories be they rich, destitute, young or old.

Recommendations

To this end, based on the findings in this research, the following recommendations are made.

It is recommended that:

- i. Widow empowerment scheme of the book of Ruth be noted and understood.
- ii. Counseling should be clearly understood as an empowerment.
- iii. Widows should be understood to be of different categories (younger, older, destitute, plebeian etc.) and should not be treated homogeneously in counselling.
- iv. Counselor should understand cultural variations about widowhood and use this knowledge in addressing widows of different cultures.

- v. Counselor should understand variation of widows' need, and individualise widows in provision of counseling services.
- vi. Unless, they are not interested for some genuine reason(s), younger widows should be encouraged to remarry and the pastor counselor should help the families concerned to understand the need for this.
- vii. There should be more public sensitisation on younger widows' remarriage.
- viii. Pastoral counselor should embrace and utilise widow empowerment schema of the book of Ruth for effective and focused widow counseling.

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